

more abundant and because the likelihood is greater that an insect will become a carrier when infected plants are present longer.

In the 1981 wet season, RTD broke out in an irrigated, double-cropped area of Nueva Ecija, Philippines, where we were studying the relationship between insect pest distribution and asynchronizing planting. We selected 14 sites at regular intervals along two transects paralleling irrigation flows.

Using maps and data provided by the irrigation authority, we calculated the planting asynchrony around each site as the standard deviation of planting date (transformed to a cardinal value) in all fields within defined radii (0.2-2.0 km). Insect abundance was measured as total catch over the season in two simple kerosene light traps installed at each site.

We estimated the prevalence of RTD at six sites as the mean infection rate in five fields (150 hills/field) randomly selected within the rotational area (30-ha irrigation management unit) containing the light traps. Diagnosis was based

1. RTD infection at 6 sites in relation to the asynchrony of planting within 0.6 km, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1981 wet season. The best-fitting equation is $Y = -9.12 + 1.28 X$, where Y is arcsin-transformed.

2. RTD infection at 6 sites in relation to the seasonal abundance of GLH. ○ = 1981 wet season; ● = 1982 dry season. The best-fitting equation is $Y = -24.26 + 4.44 X$, where Y is arcsin-transformed.

on visual symptoms and confirmed by starch-iodine test.

RTD prevalence increased with asynchrony of planting within 0.6 km of the sites (maximum correlation $r = 0.83$, $P < 0.05$) (Fig. 1). The abundances of green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix* spp. and of the most efficient vector *N. virescens* were also maximally correlated ($P < 0.05$) with asynchrony within 0.6 km (Fig. 2). This suggests that the mean net displacement of these species over a season is limited.

Other parameters (mean varietal maturity, area devoted to rice, intensity of insecticide use) failed to account for significant additional variation in either disease prevalence or insect abundance.

RTD recurred the following dry season, but estimates of asynchronizing planting were not available. However, taking both seasons together, disease prevalence was significantly correlated with the abundance of both GLH ($r = 0.69$, $P < 0.02$; Fig. 2) and *N. virescens* ($r = 0.61$, $P < 0.05$). □

Field evaluation to control "red stripe," a new rice disease in Vietnam

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"Red stripe" was recorded for the first time in the Mekong Delta in 1988 dry season. The disease developed rapidly in the summer and autumn of 1990. Severe attack caused up to 50% yield loss, due to premature senescence and high ratios of unfilled grain.

We tested the effects of some pesticides on red stripe at disease CLRRI experimental fields. The rice cultivar used was OM59-7. Plot size was 5 × 4 m, 20 × 10-cm plant spacing, in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Fertilizer was applied at 100-60-00 kg NPK/ha. All fungicides except one were applied twice, 7 d before

Table 1. Fungicides effective against rice red stripe disease.^a CLRRI, Omon, Haugiang, summer-autumn 1990.

Chemical	Dosage (parts/thousand)	Time of application	Disease severity		Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
			% leaves with disease at 7 DAS	% leaf area covered by disease at 14 DAS		
Copper-benlate mixture	2	7 DBH	28.66	12.05	34.9	2.7
Benlate 50 % WP	3	7 DBH	19.86	2.44	36.6	2.4
Triphenyltin-acetate 60 % WP	3	7 DBH	35.84	13.69	36.1	2.4
Oryzemat 8 % G + carbendazim 6 % WP	4 kg ai/ha	20 DBH-7 DBH	18.75	0.01	38.5	2.2
Control (unsprayed)	-	-	46.95	52.99	45.1	2.0
LSD (0.01)			15.21	10.86		
(0.05)					6.4	ns

^aDAS = days after spraying, DBH = days before heading.

heading (DBH) and 7 d after heading, using a knapsack sprayer (vol 500 liters/ha). Oryzemat 8% G was applied once at 20 DBH.

Disease severity was measured 7 and 14 d after the second spraying. When disease levels were low, leaves with symptoms were counted in 50-leaf samples. When disease levels were high,

the percentage leaf area covered by disease lesions was measured. Fifty samples were taken in each plot.

Carbendazim, benlate, copper-benlate mixture, and triphenyltin acetate were effective against red stripe disease (Table 1). Kasuran and Oryzemat had no effect (Table 2). □

Table 2. Fungicides not effective against rice red stripe disease.^a CLRR1, Omon, Haugiang, summer-autumn 1990.

Chemical	Dosage (parts/thousand)	Time of application	Disease severity		Unfilled grains/panicle (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
			% leaves with disease at 7 DAS	% leaf area covered by disease at 14 DAS		
Kitazin 50 % EC	2	7 DAH	23.23	23.85	38.1	4.4
Hinosan 40 % EC	2.0	7 DAH	22.77	50.07	38.5	4.9
Kasuran 20 % WP	1.5	7 DAH	26.68	51.47	48.4	4.1
Oryzemat 8 % G	4 kg ai/ha	20 DBH	25.78	52.13	33.3	4.6
Control (unsprayed)	-	-	23.36	61.17	41.3	4.4
LSD (0.05)			ns	19.52	ns	ns

^a DAH = days after heading, DAS = days after spraying, DBH = days before heading.

Integrated pest management—insects

A parasitoid of stalk-eyed fly eggs in West Africa

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During ecological investigations on the stalk-eyed fly (SEF) *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart, in 1989 wet season at IITA in southwestern Nigeria, we introduced SEF eggs into an experimental field to explore indigenous parasitoids.

Potted plants of rice cultivar Suakoko 8 carrying 1-d-old eggs from a screenhouse culture of SEF were exposed for 1 d in ricefields each week for 2 mo. Exposed

eggs were incubated in the laboratory in glass vials with a wet wad of cotton.

Three to four trichogrammatid wasps developed from each SEF egg. Upon dissection, each SEF egg showed as many as 8-9 larval/pupal stages of the parasitoids. Superparasitism was 12-15%. The developmental period of the parasitoid was 7-9 d.

The parasitoid was identified as *Trichogramma* sp. near *kalkae* Schulten & Feijen. This species has the distinctive genitalia characteristic of *T. kalkae*, a species found in SEF eggs in Malawi. However, the antennae of *T. sp.* near *kalkae* resemble those of *T. mandelai* Pintureau & Babault, found in eggs of Noctuidae (Lepidoptera) from Chad.

It may be that *T. sp.* near *kalkae* has not yet been described, or that the degree of intraspecific variation in genitalia characters or antennae is great. □

A population of brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes 1 and 2 mixture in Guangdong, China

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Guangdong in South China is the primary area of BPH immigration from Southeast Asia. BPH biotypes 2 and 3 are already present in the Philippines, Indonesia,

Vietnam, and the Solomon Islands. In June 1990, we collected a BPH colony in Gaozhou county, Guangdong, and isolated BPH biotypes 2 and 3.

For biotype evaluation, progenies of these BPH were evaluated using seedling bulk and survival rate tests. IR26 and Mudgo with the *Bph 1* resistance gene, IR36 and ASD7 with *bph 2*, IR56 with *Bph 3*, and TN1 with no resistance gene were used as identifying varieties.

Gravid BPH females were caged on 35-d-old plants of IR26, Mudgo, and ASD7, with 20 replications. First-

generation nymphs were evaluated on IR26, Mudgo, ASD7, and TN1 in the seedling bulk test. If some of the progenies damaged IR26, Mudgo, or ASD7 seedlings, the insects were mass-reared on TN1 for seedling bulk and survival rate tests.

In the seedling bulk tests, each 7-d-old rice seedling in the mass seedbox was infested with 10 newly hatched nymphs. When TN1 seedlings died, responses of all varieties were rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice scale*. In survival rate tests, 10 third- to fourth-instar nymphs were caged on 35-d-old potted rice plants, with five replications per variety. BPH were counted 10 d after infestation.

Two and one replications of nymphs isolated with IR26 and Mudgo damaged IR26 and Mudgo seedlings, respectively. However, nymphs isolated with ASD7 did not damage IR26, Mudgo, or ASD7.

A progeny from a female isolated on

Damage rating

1. Damage rating to rice varieties infested with Gaozhou BPH colony and SC26 BPH population.

Survival (%)

2. Survival rate of SC26 BPH population. Bars with a common letter are not significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test (P 0.05).